

Decoding the charge carrier dynamics in triple cation based perovskites solar cells

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Deciphering charge carrier dynamics in perovskites solar cells (PSCs) and electrical merits are essential to further improve the performance and operational stability. We investigated the charge carrier dynamics in triple cation-based PSCs through temperature dependence electrochemical impedance spectra, thermal admittance spectroscopy, and space charge limited current (SCLC). The measured temperature dependence capacitance versus frequency ($C-f$) spectra reveal two kinds of activation process: (i) low-frequency at higher temperature (>260 K), and (ii) high-frequency at a lower temperature (< 260 K). The evaluated activation energy (E_A) at a high temperature from all three experiments was found to be in the range of $0.255 - 0.266$ eV, which corresponds to activate the migration of halide anion, whereas the low-temperature activation process stems from the trapping/de-trapping of electronic charges from shallow traps. The trap density of states in triple cation ($10^{15} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) was evaluated to be over two to six orders of magnitude lower than typically used single cation-based perovskites, while charge carrier mobility ($5.76 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{V.s}$) evaluated from the SCLC technique was nearly an order of magnitude higher than single cation perovskites.

1. Introduction

Mixed-cations and mixed-halide $[\text{FA}_y\text{MA}_z\text{Cs}_{1-y-z}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_a\text{Br}_b\text{Cl}_{1-a-b})_3]$ based perovskites solar cells (PSCs) delivered excellent device performance^{1,2} and showed improved stability against humidity and temperature as compared to single cation FA/MA/Cs perovskites.^{3,4} The mixing of cation allows tuning of direct energy bandgap of the perovskites layer⁵⁻⁷ and improves PSCs environmental stabilities.⁸ The triple cation perovskites provide structural stability, retard the formation of the yellow phase which adversely impacts the photovoltaics (PV) performance. Further, higher reproducibility, thermal, and moisture stability were shown by triple cation as compared to single or double cations based-PSCs.⁹⁻¹² Additionally, the incorporation of Cs in perovskites mitigates ion migration, subsequently reduces the halide segregation problem in mixed halide perovskites.¹³⁻¹⁶

In PSCs, besides electronic carriers (electron and holes) several other charge species including halide anion ($X^- = \text{I}^-, \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$), halide vacancies (V_X^+), monovalent (Cs^+ , MA^+ , and FA^+), and divalent (Pb^{2+}) cations also migrate under illumination and applied bias which causes electrical instability.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ The ionic and electronic charge transport featured in PSCs can be distinguished by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).²⁰⁻²² EIS is an effective and facile technique to distinguish the physical phenomena that occur at various time scales such as charge transfer at the interface or in bulk, charge recombination, electrical and ionic transport, dielectric relaxation, etc.^{23,24} Due to the low activation energy of halide ion (X^-) migration in PSCs, X^- accumulate at the electron selective layer (ESL) interface, while the V_X^+ , concentrates at the hole selective layer (HSL) interface, leading to electrode polarization. The electrode polarization induces an additional internal electric field originating from the ESL to HSL which assists the charge carrier collection efficiency.^{25,26} To investigate these phenomena in a triple cation $[\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{FAPbI}_{3(0.81)}\text{MAPbBr}_{3(0.09)}]$ PSCs, we recorded EIS in dark as well as under illumination by varying applied bias. Further, to investigate the nature of charges accumulated at the perovskites/charge selective contact interface, we measured EIS spectra in both forward and reverse bias by changing the polarity of the device. The measured EIS were analyzed by fitting with equivalent circuit (EC) and key electrical parameters were extracted. It is common knowledge, that halide perovskites are prone to defects due to their soft crystal lattice that causes lattice distortion and consequently have very low defect formation energies.¹⁸ The presence of impurities, local variation in polarization energy, or electrode polarization are other reasons for the formation of defects in PSCs.²⁸⁻³⁰ Moreover, due to the low activation energy for halide anion migration, cationic vacancies are also present in the perovskites absorbing layer.³¹ The charge carriers are captured by these defect states (created due to distortion in perovskites lattice, grain boundaries, or impurity or halide vacancies) and are termed as traps that hinder the transport of photogenerated charge carriers to respective electrodes, subsequently, deteriorate device performance. Further, the presence of traps causes Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) non-radiative recombination³², $J-V$ hysteresis³³, charge scattering³⁴, a decrease in electron-hole diffusion length, and reduction in device open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}).³⁵ Moreover, defect also impact the device stability and accelerate the degradation. Once the charge carrier gets trapped in these trap states its fate is determined by the nature of the trap it gets captured. A trap state that resides within the bandgap can capture the charge carriers, whereas trap states residing above (below) the conduction band (valence band) edge have no adverse impact on the charge transport properties of free carriers.³⁶ If carriers get trapped in shallow traps near the band edge, having a depth less than the thermal energy i.e.

$$\Delta E \leq k_B T \cong 25 \text{ meV}$$

it can be detrapped again by thermal energy or optical excitations. These traps only restrict the efficient movement of free carriers through trapping and detrapping processes. On the other hand, deep trap states exist near the mid of the energy gap having depth $\Delta E > k_B T$ act as SRH non-radiative recombination center.

The elucidation of the nature of traps, trap distribution density, trap activation energy is of paramount importance. Several theoretical models such as DFT calculation,³⁷ first principle calculation,³⁸ and several experimental techniques including temperature-dependence photoluminescence,³⁹ transient absorption spectroscopy,⁴⁰ time-resolved fluorescence,³⁹ thermally stimulated current (TSC),⁴¹ deep-level transient spectroscopy (DLTS),⁴² space charge limited current (SCLC),⁴³ thermal admittance spectroscopy (TAS),^{44,45} and capacitance-voltage (C-V) measurements⁴⁶ have been employed to analyze the traps presents in PSCs. TAS in a combination of Mott-Schottky analyses (C-V plot) provides a complete *i.e.* both quantities and qualitative information of traps in PSCs. It provides the trap density, distribution of traps, depth of traps present as well as trapping/de-trapping of charge carriers. Besides, TAS provides information on the device's underlying mechanism, which is challenging to unravel by other techniques. Moreover, the important electrical parameters such as dielectric constant, built-in voltage, depletion width at perovskites/charge selective contact (CSC) junction, interfacial charge accumulation, electrode polarization, dielectric relaxation, which impact the performance of PSCs can also be extracted from this technique. In the present work, we investigated traps in triple-cation PSCs by measuring temperature-dependence capacitance–frequency (C-f) spectra, and the Mott-Schottky plot and aforementioned parameters have been evaluated. We noted two different kinds of activation processes, i) one at low frequency (< 1 kHz) and high temperature (>260 K) and, ii) other at high frequency (> 1 kHz) and low temperature (< 260 K) attributed to halides anions migration and electronic transport, respectively.

Results and discussion

The charge transport properties of PSCs were investigated in normal *n-i-p* device configuration viz. FTO/c-TiO₂/mp-TiO₂/Cs_{0.1}(FAPbI₃)_{0.81}(MAPbBr₃)_{0.09}/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au as depicted (Figure 1a). The *J-V* characteristics under illumination (Figure 1b), showed the fabricated PSC exhibits a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 18.78% in forward scan (FS) and 18.12% in reverse scan (RS). The electrical response of the fabricated PSCs was investigated by measuring EIS as a function of applied bias and photovoltage (Figure 2a-c). All spectra display two semicircles and are analyzed by an equivalent circuit (Figure 2d). The resistance R_S is the contact series resistance (e.g. electrodes, connecting wires, etc.). The resistance R_1 together with the constant phase element (CPE1) analyzes the high-frequency (HF) semicircle, whereas the low-frequency (LF) part of the spectra was analyzed by a parallel R-C circuit containing R_2 and CPE2.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic diagram of *n-i-p* based perovskite solar cell studied, and (b) *J-V* characteristics of the device under illumination.

The constant phase elements CPE1 and CPE2 were used for rational fitting of EIS spectra (attributed to the inhomogeneous perovskites layer and interface) rather than pure capacitance C_1 and C_2 .⁴⁴ The variation of fitting parameters as a function of applied bias and photovoltage is illustrated in Fig. S1-S2. The high-frequency capacitance C_1 is associated with geometrical capacitance and bulk dielectric relaxation of the perovskite layer.³¹ The value of C_1 was evaluated to be $\sim 4.50 \times 10^{-8}$ or 9.18×10^{-8} Fcm⁻² at short circuit (SC) condition, slightly increases in forward bias (FB) and decreases in reverse bias (RB) (Figure S1a) but remains of the order of 10^{-8} Fcm⁻². The relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of the perovskites was derived from the relation:

$$C_g = \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 A / L$$

where $\epsilon_0 = 8.86 \times 10^{-14}$ F/cm is the permittivity of free space, $A = 0.49$ cm², and $L = 400$ nm are device active area and thickness of perovskites layer, respectively. The evaluated value of dielectric constant from high-frequency capacitance was found to be 41.5 which is in agreement with the measured value of ~ 44 from *C-f* spectra of perovskites layer sandwiched between two gold electrodes (Figure S3).⁴⁷ Moreover, a similar value of C_1 dominates the capacitive response at room temperature in the frequency region of >1 kHz of the *C-f* spectra of fabricated PSCs (Figure 4a). Furthermore, the dielectric constant of triple-cation perovskites is higher than single or double cation perovskites (Table S1).

It can be deduced from Fig. S1a, that the high-frequency capacitance (C_1) increases in forward bias and decreases in reverse bias. The increase in capacitance, C_1 can be explained in terms of decrease of depletion width under forward bias which enables the migration of electronic and ionic charges inside the perovskite layer. In contrast, the depletion width increases under reverse bias,

subsequently free carrier density decreases owing to the reduction in geometrical capacitance. Further, high-frequency resistance, R_1 (Figure S1c) is the charge transport resistance (R_{ct}) in the bulk perovskite layer,⁴⁸ observed to be decreased in forward bias whereas it increases in reverse bias. The applied forward bias enables the charge transport into the perovskite layer, as a result, decrease of charge transport resistance. However, under reverse bias, the charge carriers depleted in the perovskite layer owing to depletion width increment, consequently, increase of charge transport resistance. The capacitance C_2 responds to the prominent low-frequency mechanisms that govern the PSCs operation and has been interpreted as the accumulation of charge carriers in the vicinity of the perovskite/charge selective layer interface.⁴⁹ We noted (Figure S2 a,b) that under external forward bias or photovoltage (illumination), the low-frequency capacitance, C_2 shows an increment of over four orders in magnitude i.e. 9.79×10^{-7} F at the short circuit and 1.29×10^{-2} F at V_{oc} , however, in reverse external bias, the value of C_2 largely remains constant and slightly decreases for $V > 0.8$ V. Under the influence of forward bias or photovoltage halide ions (X^-) migrates towards HTL and accumulate in the vicinity of perovskites/HTL interface⁵⁰ causes an increase of C_2 . The evolution of low-frequency capacitance as a function of photovoltage (illumination) was fitted by the Guoy-Chapman model (Fig. S4) given by:^{51,52}

$$C_{acc} = C_2 = \left(\frac{q^2 n_{acc} \epsilon_r \epsilon_0}{2k_B T} \right)^{1/2} \exp\left(\frac{qV}{m_c k_B T} \right)$$

where n_{acc} is the ionic concentration in bulk, m_c is a capacitive exponent, k_B is Boltzmann constant and T is temperature. The interfacial accumulation region at equilibrium condition (zero bias) is given by ionic Debye length⁵³

$$L_D = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon \epsilon_0 k_B T}{q^2 n_{acc}}}$$

and corresponding ionic accumulation capacitance is:

$$C_{acc} = \frac{\epsilon \epsilon_0}{L_D}$$

The accumulation zone at zero bias was evaluated to be ~ 5.5 nm with an ionic charge density of $1.98 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, similar to reported for ionic Debye length of MAPbI_3 .⁵³ Furthermore, forward bias facilitates the ionic migration in the perovskite layer, consequently, low-frequency resistance, R_2 decrease (Figure S2c). The resistance R_2 is interpreted as electronic charge transport at the perovskite/CSC interface. Under reverse bias, the value of C_2 remains the same up to 0.8 V, then slightly decreases at higher bias. The decrease in C_2 for $V > 0.8$ V is attributed to the depopulation of accumulated ionic charges at the interface. Under the influence of high reverse bias, halide anions migrate away from the interface and compensate halide vacancies.⁵⁴ This mitigating the ionic migration in the perovskite layer, also evident from the increase of the LF resistance, R_2 (Figure S2c). Moreover, we noted (Figure 2a) that at high reverse bias (>0.8 V) two arcs merge into a single one, further confirming the mitigation of ionic migration at higher reverse bias.

Figure 2. Impedance spectra of investigated devices under (a, b) applied bias, (c) illumination, and (d) equivalent circuits used to fit the impedance data.

We deduced (Figure S1b, & Figure S2b), that under illumination/photovoltage, both C_1 and C_2 exponentially increases with an increase of illumination intensity for photovoltage of above 600 mV. The increase in C_1 is marginal and remains of the order of 10^{-8} F, whereas C_2 increases around six orders of magnitude under photovoltage. The slight increase in C_1 with illumination can be attributed to photogeneration of the charge carriers as evident from the decrease of resistance R_1 (Figure S1d). The exponential evolution of C_2 under illumination is attributed to the accumulation of photogenerated charge carriers at interface and activation of the ionic transport in perovskite layer for photovoltage >600 mV, which further confirms that C_2 is related to ionic migration in the perovskite layer. The resistance R_2 and capacitance C_2 both vary with illumination intensities due to photovoltage variation and we found that the resistance decreases and capacitance increase with an increase of illumination or increase of external bias, suggesting both R_2 and C_2 have a common origin. The time constant for these processes was calculated by:

$$\tau_1 = R_1 C_1 \text{ and}$$

$$\tau_2 = R_2 C_2 .$$

It was noticed that shorter lifetime τ_1 decreases from $10^{-4} - 10^{-6}$ s, whereas longer lifetime τ_2 remains in the range of $10^1 - 10^2$ s. The faster feature is usually ascribed to the recombination of free carriers⁴⁰ whereas, the slower feature is usually ascribed to the response from defects and ionic migration.^{55,56}

The temperature dependence capacitance vs. frequency (C - f - T) spectra (Figure 3a), exhibit two distinct features viz. (i) high-frequency region at low temperature (f_H) and (ii) low-frequency region at higher temperature (f_L), similar to reports.^{57,58} The two features in C - f - T spectra indicates the existence of two distinctive activation process in the fabricated PSCs. Almora et al. have assigned these two activation processes to the phase transition of the $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ layer from orthorhombic structure (γ -phase) to tetragonal structure (β -phase). To probe any possible effect induce in the perovskite layer structure that causes the variation in capacitance of the PSC, we measured the temperature-dependent X-ray diffraction spectra (Figure S5). In the measured temperature range, there is no structural or phase change was observed in the perovskite layer. Warner et al. observed similar C - f - T spectra in CIGS-based solar cells and assigned f_H feature to transport barrier or interfacial/buffer layer whereas the f_L was assigned to tail states at the band edges or presence of slow defect states in the bulk or at the interface.⁵⁹ To unravel the origin of these two different regions in triple cation-based PSC, we plotted the temperature dependence evolution of capacitance at different frequencies (Figure 3b). It suggests that at low- frequency (up to 1 kHz), capacitance remains constant (~ 90 nF/cm²- 95 nF/cm²) until 260 K, thereafter, an exponential evolution was observed for higher temperature. The constant value of capacitance at low temperature corresponds to the geometric capacitance of the perovskite layer. The exponential evolution of capacitance at low-frequency is attributed to the polarization of interfaces due to electronic and ionic charge accumulation at the perovskite/CSC interface.⁶⁰⁻⁶³ In contrast, the C - T graph at high-frequency exhibits the opposite behavior i.e. increase of capacitance at low temperature from 40 nF/cm²- 90 nF/cm², and achieve a constant value at high temperature. It is established that the evolution of low-frequency capacitance corresponds to ions accumulation at the interface, however, the increase of HF capacitance at a lower temperature is not frequently observed. Recently, Awni et al. have assigned the high-frequency capacitance to trapping/de-trapping of charge carriers in Spiro-OMeTAD doped with lithium (Li) and cobalt (Co) salts, whereas low-frequency signature corresponds to the defects in perovskite absorber layers or at the perovskites/CSC interfaces.⁵⁷ An ionically gated interface-transistor model was built,^{64,65} in which electronic energy barriers to injection and recombination are modulated by the accumulation/depletion of ionic charge at the interfaces. The applied ac voltage to PSCs introduces an out-of-phase capacitive ionic current which modulates the electronic recombination and injection across the interface that causes capacitive-like or inductive-like behavior without charge accumulation at the interface.^{65,66}

Figure 3. (a) C - f spectra at different temperatures, and (b) evolution of capacitance of PSC as a function of temperature at different frequencies.

To illustrate the mechanism responsible for the evolution of capacitance in high-frequency and low-frequency regions, we evaluated the activation energy (E_A) and trap density of states (N_T) by plotting $(-fdC/df)$ vs. f graph (Figure 4a and 4b). The activation energy was evaluated by plotting the Arrhenius plot between peak frequency (f_{peak}) and $1000/T$ (Figure 4c,d). The activation energy for the features f_L and f_H were calculated to be 254 meV and 91 meV, respectively.

This finding suggests that for temperatures above 260 K, halide anions start migrating in the perovskite layer in addition to electronic charges. The temperature range is following the previous reports^{31,67,68} to activate the halide anion migration in the perovskites layer. This finding suggests that the low-frequency arc in EIS and evolution of capacitance at low-frequency at high temperature is attributed to activation of ionic migration and accumulation at the perovskites/CSC interface. The extracted charge transport resistance (R_1) as a function of temperature (Figure 5e), decreases from $1 \times 10^7 \Omega$ at 130K to 596 Ω at 360 K.

Figure 4: $-fdC/df$ vs. f graph for (a) HF at low temperature and (b) LF at high temperature. (c, d) Arrhenius plot to evaluate activation energy for the process occurs at (c) HF, low temperature, and (d) LF, high temperature.

The interfacial charge transport resistance R_2 firstly decreases up to 260 K (Figure 5f), and thereafter increases and achieves a saturation value of $1 \times 10^{20} \Omega$ at 310 K. At low-temperature R_2 decreases with the increase of temperature because thermal energy assists the interfacial charge transfer at perovskite/CSC. However, as temperature increases above 260 K, halide anions start migrating towards ETL, leaving behind cationic vacancies near the HTL, resulting in the accumulation of halides anions at the perovskite/ETL interface, and develop an internal field from HTL to ETL. This internal field restricts the electronic charge transfer at the interface as a result R_2 increases beyond 260 K.

Figure 5: Temperature dependence EIS spectra (a, b). Extracted value of capacitance C_1 from EC (c), Arrhenius plot of onset frequency of LF arc (d), the resistance R_1 (e), and R_2 (f) as a function of temperature.

We measured the Mott-Schottky plot at an intermediate frequency (10 kHz) to suppress the effect of ionic migration, also in this frequency range, the depletion layer capacitance (C_{dl}) dominates the dielectric polarization capacitance (Figure 3a). The measured Mott-Schottky plot (Figure 6a) exhibits three regions.^{58,69,70} In the reverse bias, the perovskites layer is fully depleted and the device capacitance corresponds to geometrical capacitance (C_g). In forward bias, the depletion width (W) decreases which leads to an increase of capacitance following the law: $C^{-2} \propto V$ (blue line) corresponds to depletion layer capacitance C_{dl} . When forward bias approaches V_{bi} , depletion width shrinks and charge carriers accumulate at interface and capacitance exponentially increases which corresponds to interfacial electronic/ionic charge accumulation capacitance C_s .⁵⁷ Therefore, no overlapping of C_{dl} with C_s can be seen, although both regions are visible⁷¹ for the validation of the Mott-Schottky plot to extract the built-in voltage and dopant density (N) in the perovskites solar cells. The interfacial built-in voltage (V_{bi}) and depletion width (w) were, calculated from the intercept on voltage axes and slope of the blue region (C_{dl} region) respectively, from the Mott-Schottky plot (Figure 6a). The evaluated built-in voltage is 0.88 V, depletion width $w = 43$ nm, and doping density $N_d \sim 2.35 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Figure 6b shows the trap density profile as a function of demarcation energy (E_w). The peak trap density observed around 255 meV with a peak value $\sim 2.05 \times 10^{15} \text{ eVcm}^{-3}$ at 360 K. Further, the peak of trap density (255 meV) is similar to the one calculated from $C-F-T$ and EIS spectra (Figure 4d and Figure 5d), respectively. The density of the deep traps in mixed cation perovskites are lower than that of single cation based perovskites; 10^{16} – $10^{21} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$ for MAPbI₃,^{43,70,72,73} $3 \times 10^{16} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$ for MAPbI_xCl_{3-x},⁷⁴ and $10^{18} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$ for MA_{0.7}FA_{0.3}PbI₃.⁵⁷ (Table S1). Arguably, the observed variation in capacitance at low-frequency at high temperature corresponds to activation of halide ions and accumulation at perovskites/CSC interface. The density of traps for high-frequency at 130 K was evaluated to be $\sim 7.60 \times 10^{13} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$ with a peak value of around 90 meV (Figure S6) which is around two orders lower than calculated for low-frequency. With an increase of temperature, the depth of shallow traps slightly deepen (94 meV) and the density of states decreases to $6.22 \times 10^{13} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$ at 190 K, attributed to the filling of shallow traps by thermally generated charge carriers. The peak of shallow traps (90 meV) is following Figure 4c. The shallow traps are suggested to be associated with charging and discharging electronic charges in the perovskite and perovskite/CSC interface. The shallow traps have a higher charging/discharging rate and respond to external high-frequency signals whereas deep traps have a low trapping/detrapping rate and follow the low-frequency signal. With a decrease in the temperature of PSC, shallow trap states freeze out as a result decrease in capacitance.

Figure 6: (a) Mott-Schottky plot of perovskite solar cells measured at 10 kHz, and (b) distribution of defects in the perovskite layer.

To further explore the mechanism of charge transport in PSCs, J - V characteristics of the triple cation perovskites in the electron-only device were measured in the temperature range 250 K – 390 K (Figure 7a). The measured J - V characteristics show three distinct regions namely, (i) Ohmic with $\log(J)$ vs. $\log(V)$ slope equal to 1, (ii) trap-filling region with slope > 2 , and (iii) trap-filled region. With applied bias, traps are filling by free carriers in the TFL region and at transition voltage (V_{TFL}) all traps are filled and free carrier density becomes higher than trap density. Trap density (n_{trap}) was evaluated through the equation:

$$n_{trap} = 2\epsilon\epsilon_0 V_{TFL} / qL^2$$

and calculated to be $3.97 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at room temperature. The trap filling region was fitted with SCLC equation for exponentially distributed traps^{75,76}:

$$J = q^{1-l} \mu N_c \left(\frac{2l+1}{l+1} \right)^{l+1} \left(\frac{l}{l+1} \frac{\epsilon}{H_b} \right)^l \frac{V^{l+1}}{L^{2l+1}}$$

Where q is the total charge, N_c is the effective density of states at the edge of the conduction band, H_b is the density of traps at the edge of the conduction band. The fitting parameters used are: $H_b = 3.97 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_c = 5.30 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 5.76 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and characteristics trap energy

$$E_t = k_B T_C = 292 \text{ meV} \quad \text{and} \quad l = T_C / T$$

The SCLC derived charge carrier mobility in mixed cation-based PSCs ($\mu = 5.76 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) is higher than of single cation-based PSCs in both *n-i-p* ($1.11 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)⁴⁶ and *p-i-n* ($5.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)³¹ configurations. The higher carrier mobility in mixed cation than of single cation PSCs is possibly attributed due to the lower trap density in the former ($2.05 \times 10^{15} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$) than later ($10^{16} - 10^{21} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$) as illustrated in Table S1. The Arrhenius plot of current density at 0.75 V vs. $1000/T$ (Figure 7b), suggests the calculated activation energy of 0.266 eV is in a similar range as derived from capacitance and impedance spectroscopy discussed above.

Figure 7. (a) Temperature-dependent J - V characteristics, and (b) Arrhenius plot of current density at 0.75 V vs. $1000/T$.

Conclusions

We probed the charge carrier dynamics in triple cation-based perovskite solar cells by employing impedance, and C - F - T spectroscopy, along with dark J - V characteristics. By measuring bias and polarity dependence impedance spectroscopy, we interpreted both geometrical and interfacial capacitance of fabricated solar cells. The exponential increase in low-frequency capacitance in forward bias ascribes to the accumulation of ionic charge at the interface and this decreases slightly in reverse bias due to the depopulation of accumulated charges at the perovskites/charge selective contact interface. Temperature dependence C - f spectra reveal two types of the activation process, attributed to ionic migration and charging/discharging of shallow traps. The traps density of states in mixed cation-based solar cells ($2.45 \times 10^{15} \text{ eV/cm}^3$) is lower than that of single or double cation-based perovskite solar cells, owing to the better structural stability. The dark J - V characteristics of electron-only devices display typical SCLC behavior with exponential distribution of traps and carrier mobility evaluated to be nearly an order of magnitude higher than single cation-based perovskite. Temperature-dependent diffractograms reveal no phase transition or structural changes in the investigated temperature range for triple cation perovskite, suggesting the temperature-dependent electrical properties variation does not stem from phase transitions and is ascribed to the activation of ionic transport and interfacial effect. Our results quantify the merits of triple cation-based solar cells and ascribed to superior charge transport properties in terms of enhanced carrier mobility, lower trap density, and stable perovskite structure.

Experimental section

Materials: The chemicals for perovskite were obtained from Dyesol except for PbI_2 and CsI_2 that were procured from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI) and were utilized as such. 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(N,N-di-p-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) was acquired from Merck KGaA. Lithium bis-(trifluoromethylsulphonyl)imide (LiTFSI) and 4-tert-butylpyridine (t-BP) were acquired from Sigma Aldrich. 30NRD TiO_2 was obtained from Dyesol.

Device fabrication: The laser-etched FTO-coated glasses (NSG10) were thoroughly cleaned via ultra-sonication with Hellmanex II solution, deionized water, acetone, ethanol, and isopropanol for 20 min each step. The dried substrates using compressed air were further treated by UV-ozone for 30 min before device fabrication. TiO_2 compact layer was deposited using spray pyrolysis at 500 °C employing 1 mL of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetyl acetonate) precursor solution (75% in 2-propanol) in 19 mL of pure ethanol using oxygen as a carrier gas, followed by annealing for another 30 min at 500 °C to acquire the anatase phase. Once the substrates were cooled down to room temperature, the TiO_2 mesoporous layer (1:8 w/v in ethanol) was spin-coated at 4000 rpm (2000 rpm/s acceleration) for 30 s, followed by a progressive heating step until 500 °C for 30 min. After cooling down the samples were transferred immediately to the argon-filled glovebox under controlled moisture and oxygen conditions (H_2O level: <1 ppm and O_2 level: <10 ppm) to prevent moisture absorption to the ETM layer. The triple-cation perovskite layers were deposited through a

one-step method.⁷⁷ The perovskite precursor solution was prepared by CsI (0.10M), FAI (1.05 M), PbI₂ (1.24 M), MABr (0.12 M), and PbBr₂ (0.12 M) in an anhydrous solvent mixture of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) with 4:1 vol ratio. The precursor solution was spin-coated in a two-step spin-coating program (1000 rpm and 6000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively) and 112 μ L of chlorobenzene was dripped at 10 s before ending the second spin step followed by annealing at 100 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 h for perovskite crystallization. Spiro-OMeTAD (70mM) was prepared by dissolving the desired amount of material in 1mL chlorobenzene together with 38.4 μ L of 4-tert-butylpyridine and 21.1 μ L of bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt (520 mg in 1 mL acetonitrile). 35 μ L of HTM solution was dropped on the perovskite layer and were spin-coated at 4000 rpm for 20 s. Au electrode (80 nm) was thermally evaporated under a pressure of 2×10^{-6} Pa.

Device characterization. The current density-voltage (*J-V*) curves were performed using a Keithley 2400 source meter under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW/cm² illumination from a 450 W AAA Oriol solar simulator (94023 A). NREL certified monocrystalline silicon solar cell was used for calibration. The active area was defined by a laser-cut black metal mask (0.09cm²). The *J-V* measurements under illumination conditions were performed at a scan rate: 500 mV/s with 10 s pre-sweep delay. IPCE measurements were recorded using a 150 W xenon lamp attached to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4 m monochromator. The impedance spectroscopy was performed in the frequency range of 2 MHz – 100 mHz under the perturbation of 20 mV ac signal using Biologic SP300 Potentiostat and a white LED (for illumination conditions) in a faradaic chamber. Temperature-dependent capacitance-frequency measurements were performed with LCR meter model No. E4980A along with a Linkam (LTS420) sample heating control system filled with liquid nitrogen in a closed environment. The temperature was adjusted using LabVIEW (NI) software. The temperature-dependence dark *J-V* characteristics were measured using Keithley 2604 source meter together with the Linkam system.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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